

Influence of furcellaran and safflower oil concentration on the properties of model emulgel systems

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of varying concentrations of furcellaran (FUR) and safflower (*Carthamus Tinctorius*) oil on the functional properties of emulgels as potential carriers of bioactive substances. The textural, mechanical, thermal and structural properties of twenty different formulations were characterised. The pH stability and zeta-potential of the emulgels was also examined. It was found clear correlation between gelling agent and oil fraction content and investigated properties. The hardness, strength, thermal stability expressed as melting point of the investigated systems increased with increasing concentration of the furcellaran and decreasing proportion of safflower oil, which indicated a significant weakening of the structure as a result of the addition of the oil fraction. Stored under refrigeration, emulgels appeared to be relatively stable showing a slight decrease in pH values after 7 days. Swelling ratio (SW) of emulgels increased with increasing both, polysaccharide and oil content, in emulgels. Based on the microstructure analyses, it can also be concluded that only part of the added safflower oil chemically bound to the functional groups of the polysaccharide, while the vast majority of it was only physically immobilized in the furcellaran matrix. Colour of furcellaran – safflower oil emulsion gels depended largely on the amount of oil fraction. The presented research demonstrating the wide spectrum of functional properties of polysaccharide-oil systems is a first step to developing a carrier composition for lipophilic compounds at further stages of research.

1. Introduction

Emulsion gels known also as emulgels, emulsion hydrogels and emulsion-filled gels have recently attracted growing interest because due to their properties they are used in various industries such as food [1], cosmetics [2] and pharmaceuticals [3]. High popularity of emulsion gels resulted from advantages such as semi-solid structure containing a high percentage of water, resistance to undesirable chemical reactions such as hydrolysis and oxidation or high physical stability that prevents phase separation. Considering their homogeneous structure containing both hydrophilic and lipophilic components, emulgels are a great carrier

for bioactive fat-soluble compounds such as vitamins, essential fatty acids and carotenoids. Moreover, many food and drug applications rely on the ability of emulsion gels to control and prolong the release of specific compounds in the gastrointestinal tract due to their protection by the gel matrix. Gelled emulsions containing vegetable oils with beneficial omega acid composition and spreadable consistency are used as analogues of animal fat in meat and dairy products [4–6]. Due to their ease of spreading, ability to adjust viscosity, and skin compatibility, emulgels are typically used in the cosmetics industry as topical formulations [7,8]. Structurally, emulgels are colloidal complexes containing emulsion droplets which, depending on the way they are bound, can

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belong to one of two groups: droplet-filled gels or emulsion droplet-aggregated gels. The first includes materials with a polymer matrix supporting hydrophobic emulsion fractions, while in the second, emulsion droplets form a network that penetrates and disrupts the gel matrix. In practice, emulgels usually contain both structures [7] and the selection of adequate components and production method allows the development of materials with a wide range of mechanical, rheological or functional properties. In food technology, emulsion gels are usually produced based on a matrix of biomacromolecules: proteins or polysaccharides. Systems with a matrix of gelatine [9], whey protein [10], soy protein [11] or caseinate [12] were widely discussed. Pectin [13], modified starches [14], inulin [15] or chitosan [16] are often used to produce polysaccharide-stabilized emulsions. Also emulgels using seaweed polysaccharides such as agar [17], alginate [18] or carrageenan [19] have been investigated in many studies and reviews [20,21]. Composite-matrixes combining two materials such as polysaccharide and protein [22] or even three different polymers [23] are also of an increasing research interest. However, until now, there is a lack of reports on the properties of emulsion-filled gels containing a matrix formed by furcellaran.

Obtained from red algae *Furcellaria lumbricalis* furcellaran is negatively charged linear polysaccharide, composed of units consisting of a fragment of (1 → 3) β-D-galactopyranose with a sulphate group at C-4 and (1 → 4)-3,6-anhydro-α-D-galactopyranose. Extraction of furcellaran from algal biomass is currently carried out mainly in Canada and Estonia. FUR is often compared to kappa-carrageenan nevertheless in the list of food additives, was classified as a separate (E408) gelling agent. In contrast to kappa-carrageenan, furcellaran lower degree of sulfation which also explains the differences in gelation kinetics, thermal resistance and mechanical properties of gels in the presence of various ions [24–26]. Unlike other popular hydrocolloids, FUR is not used commercially on a large scale. Its present applications are mainly limited to confectionery and meat products. Current scientific reports on the potential for wider use of furcellaran are mainly focused on the production of biodegradable and active food films as an alternative to synthetic plastics [27]. It has also been shown that the polymer can be successfully used in the encapsulation processes of active compounds [28,29]. In our previous work [30], gummy jellies prepared with furcellaran were characterised by good textural and functional properties which was promising for the application of FUR in simple three-component gelled emulsion systems. The ability to form strong firm gels by heat-induction or in the presence of specific ions, as well as the fast rate of solidification, suggests that emulgels containing a furcellaran matrix will be stable even with a high proportion of the lipophilic fraction. Moreover, the presence of hydroxyl and sulphate groups confirm that furcellaran may be part of composite materials. Due to the high correlation between the gel characteristics and its formulation or process parameters (time, pH temperature, stirring speed), it may result in obtaining emulsion gels with very diversified properties, adjusted to the specific application, including being the carrier of bioactive substances. The presence of a hydrophilic and hydrophobic fraction, in addition to the stable and compact structure of furcellaran-based emulgels, might enable the controlled release of health-promoting components and prevent their degradation (for example lipids oxidation).

Safflower oil (*Carthamus tinctorius L.*) is of increasing interest to producers in the food and cosmetic industries because it has significantly higher concentration of some health-promoting compounds than other popular vegetable fats such as sunflower oil or olive oil. It is known for a very high proportion of polyunsaturated fatty acids with a predominance of linoleic acid, and is a good source of tocopherols and phenolic compounds. It has been proven that safflower oil consumption can positively affect sugar metabolism, prevent atherosclerosis, rheumatoid disease, atherosclerosis and ostischemic myocardial dysfunction. It also has hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory and antiestrogenic properties [31,32]. Moreover, due to its functional properties such as low melting

point, high freezing resistance, odor and colour stability, it can be used in complex systems such as emulsions [33] or emulgels [34].

Regardless of the branch of industry, the commercial use of emulgels as a carrier of health-promoting substances requires knowledge of their mechanical, thermal and functional properties that determine, for example, the mechanism of digestion or the controlled release of active compounds. At the moment, there are no reports on the characteristics of gels from emulsions based on furcellaran and safflower oil. Therefore, the purpose of this paper was to determine the effect of the concentration of the polysaccharide and fat fractions on the functional properties of emulgels containing safflower oil and furcellaran. The scope of work included the preparation of twenty model systems of emulgels with different polysaccharide concentrations and varied ratios of hydro and lipophilic fractions. The characterization of the final emulgel systems included the determination of physical features, thermal and textural properties, as well as the microstructure and morphology of the samples. The influence of the emulsion composition on their colour and the change in their pH during refrigerated storage was also examined.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

To prepare gelled emulsion systems following materials were employed: furcellaran type 7000 (Est-Agar AS, Karla village, Estonia), cold-pressed safflower oil (Olvita, Myslaków, Poland) and Tween 20 (Chemland, Stargard, Poland).

2.2. Emulgel systems preparation

Twenty variants of furcellaran – safflower oil emulgel were produced according to the formulation shown in Table 1. Furcellaran distilled water solutions with different concentration (2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5 and 4.0 % w/v) were prepared by stirring on a heated magnetic stirrer (MR Hei-Tec, Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG, Schwabach, Bayern, Germany) continuously for 12 h at 80 °C. Rotation speed was set at 500 rpm. Safflower oil and Tween 20 were added to the furcellaran solutions in the amounts shown in Table 1 and the mixture was homogenised (10 min, 15,000 rpm) without turning off heating set at 80 °C using a Polytron PT2500E homogeniser (Dan-Lab, Białystok, Poland). Next, the emulsions were immediately poured into hexagonal prism molds and cooled at 4 °C in the refrigerator for 12 h. Between analyses, the final samples were stored under refrigeration in hermetic containers.

2.3. Physical evaluation

2.3.1. Swelling properties measurement

The ability of the swelling of the prepared furcellaran – safflower oil emulgels were determined by sample soaking in a 0.02 % sodium azide water solution for 48 h. Experiment was performed in triplicate. The emulgels swelling ratio (SW) was calculated by using following equation:

$$SW = \frac{w_2 - w_1}{w_1} \times 100\%$$

where w_1 is the weight of the sample before soaking and w_2 is the weight of the emulsion gel after soaking.

2.3.2. Emulgels pH stability

The pH values of the developed emulgels during storage at 4 °C were measured after 1, 7 and 14 days by using digital pH-meter CP-551 (Elmetron, Poland). The measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.3.3. Zeta potential

The zeta potential of the gel-forming solutions was determined by

Table 1

Furcellaran – safflower oil emulgels formulation for 100 ml of final gel-forming solution.

Sample code	Furcellaran solution concentration [%]	Furcellaran solution [ml]	Safflower oil [ml]	TWEEN 20 [ml]
2.0 % F-A	2.0	95.0	5.0	1.6
2.0 % F-B	2.0	90.0	10.0	3.3
2.0 % F-C	2.0	85.0	15.0	5.0
2.0 % F-D	2.0	80.0	20.0	6.7
2.5 % F-A	2.5	95.0	5.0	1.6
2.5 % F-B	2.5	90.0	10.0	3.3
2.5 % F-C	2.5	85.0	15.0	5.0
2.5 % F-D	2.5	80.0	20.0	6.7
3.0 % F-A	3.0	95.0	5.0	1.6
3.0 % F-B	3.0	90.0	10.0	3.3
3.0 % F-C	3.0	85.0	15.0	5.0
3.0 % F-D	3.0	80.0	20.0	6.7
3.5 % F-A	3.5	95.0	5.0	1.6
3.5 % F-B	3.5	90.0	10.0	3.3
3.5 % F-C	3.5	85.0	15.0	5.0
3.5 % F-D	3.5	80.0	20.0	6.7
4.0 % F-A	4.0	95.0	5.0	1.6
4.0 % F-B	4.0	90.0	10.0	3.3
4.0 % F-C	4.0	85.0	15.0	5.0
4.0 % F-D	4.0	80.0	20.0	6.7

dynamic light scattering (DLS) via the Zetasizer Nano ZS Malvern apparatus (Malvern Panalytical, Malvern Worcestershire, United Kingdom) using optically homogeneous polystyrene cuvettes (measuring range 0.6 nm–6 μm) and with a detection angle of 173°. The solutions were prepared for measurement, where 1 ml of solution was taken from each sample of gel-forming solutions and then 50 ml of distilled water was added. The solutions prepared in this way were mixed on a magnetic stirrer (MR Hei-Tec, Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG, Schwabach, Bayern) at room temperature (~22 °C) until a homogeneous appearance was achieved.

2.4. Texture analysis

The texture properties of the emulgels were evaluated by two-bite compression test using Shimadzu EZ Test EZ-LX (Shimadzu, Japan) universal testing machine equipped with a load cell of 500 N. Each sample was compressed twice to 50 % of its original height with 36 mm diameter cylindrical press jig, which allowed jelly to deform without penetration. The test speed was 1 mm/s and trigger point were 0.05 N. Based on TPA curves textural parameters (hardness, springiness, cohesiveness and gumminess) were calculated using Trapezium X (Shimadzu, Japan) software. Analyses were carried out in 8 replicates.

2.5. Mechanical properties

Mechanical parameters of furcellaran – safflower oil emulgels were

determined by uniaxial compression test using EZ-test (Shimadzu, Japan) equipment, via Trapezium X software. Before analysis samples were stored at 4 °C in the refrigerator. Compression was performed using a cylinder with the dimension of 30 × 30 mm at a rate of 1 mm/s with a plate with a diameter of 40 mm, until a 50 % deformation rate was obtained. The fracture stress, elastic modulus and fracture energy were determined in three replicates for each emulgels formulation.

2.6. Colour measurement

The emulgel surface colour was evaluated using the method of reflection with the Color i5 spectrometer (X-Rite, Grand Rapids MI, USA, illuminant D65). The parameters L*, a* and b* were measured in five replicates, and the average values were calculated. The whiteness index (WI) and yellowness index (YI) was calculated using the following Equations:

$$WI = 100 - \sqrt{(100 - L^*)^2 + (a^*)^2 + (b^*)^2}$$

$$YI = \frac{142.86 \times b^*}{L^*}$$

2.7. DSC measurement

Melting characteristics of the furcellaran – safflower oil emulgels were determined by differential scanning calorimeter DSC DSC 204F1 Phoenix (Netzsch, Germany). Emulgels samples (about 10 mg) were hermetically closed in aluminium pans and analysed at DSC temperature from –80 to 200 °C with heat rate 5 °C/min. An empty aluminium pan was used as a reference and a nitrogen was applied as a carrier gas. Obtained thermograms were analysed by using Proteus Analysis (Netzsch, Germany) software. The onset melting temperature (To), peak temperature (Tm), end temperature (Te) and melting enthalpy (ΔH) were determined. Test were performed in triplicate.

2.8. Scanning electron microscopy

The morphology and local microstructure of furcellaran enriched emulgels were examined by using the Quattro ESEM microscope (ThermoFisher Scientific) equipped with FEG (field emission gun, ETD, Everhart-Thornley detector). SEM images of samples cross-sections were performed by ESEM mode (low-vacuum, 100 Pa), at magnifications ranging from 50× to 1600× and with the accelerating voltage of 5 kV. The samples were tested without prior coating. By using water vapour pressures of up to several hundred Pa, ESEM allows naturally hydrated samples to be imaged without coating with a conductive metallic layer.

2.9. X-ray diffraction

Furcellaran-safflower oil emulsion gels were analysed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using Cu Kα1 radiation (Bruker D8 Advance ECO, Germany).

2.10. Data analysis

Averages and standard deviations of samples were reported based on the minimum triplicate tests. Statistica (StatSoft, Inc., USA) software version 13.3. was used to perform Multi-factor Analyses of Variance (MANOVA) and Tukey test in order to determine whether the effect of the variables on the product was significant. Data was not showing a normal distribution were transformed according to the Box-Cox method. For the other variables significant difference ($p < 0.05$) were evaluated using one-way ANOVA with the Tukey test.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical evaluation

3.1.1. Swelling ratio of emulgels

Swelling properties and syneresis ratio greatly determine the nature of digestion and the mechanism of release of individual bioactive substances. Furcellaran - safflower oil emulsion gels did not release water at all under high-speed centrifugation (water holding capacity method) as well as did not show any syneresis (syneresis rate measurement) in the freezing test (data not shown). Water activity of all tested systems was higher than 0.99. Therefore, the initial indicator of behaviour in a neutral pH environment was swelling ratio values.

Fig. 1 shows that swelling ratio of furcellaran – safflower oil emulgels increased with the increasing both oil and hydrocolloid fraction. The same observation was also presented for emulsion gels produced using alginate [35] and pectin - soy protein isolate [36] hydrophilic matrix. An extension of the distance between the fat droplets and the matrix, resulting in the formation of water-retaining pores in the material's structure, may be responsible for the increase in SW values as a result of the increased proportion of oil in the material. In addition, increasing oil concentrations in the sample also caused a decreasing percentage of moisture, thus making some of the hydrophilic furcellaran groups free to bind more external water [37]. Confirmation that the amount of free hydrophilic groups in the polysaccharide influences the swelling ratio is also validated by the fact that water absorption increases with increasing furcellaran concentration. The SW value of emulgels with 5 % oil increased almost twofold from 9.2 to 18.0 as a result of increasing the FUR concentration from 2.0 to 4.0 %. The swelling ratio, which is measured in specific to simulate digestion, depends on a large number of factors. In addition to the concentration of the emulgel components, the interaction between them, the pH of the environment, the average droplet size of the dispersed phase or the porosity are also important. Therefore, the relationship between the swelling properties of studied emulgels and the concentration of the gelling agent and oil can be changed even with a slight modification of the formulation. Therefore, the next step of the research on the use of furcellaran - safflower oil systems as a carrier of bioactive substances will be to investigate swelling behaviour and evaluation of the release of active ingredient under simulated digestion conditions with different pH medium.

3.1.2. Emulgels pH stability during storage

Values of pH determined for furcellaran - safflower oil emulsion gels

after manufacture and refrigerated storage for 7 and 14 days were shown in Table 2. Since the studied emulgels are considered as model systems, their pH was not adjusted at the production stage, so all obtained results are a combination of chemical composition and storage time. On day one, the pH of the emulgels varied between 4.5 and 6.8 and there was a clear trend of increasing pH with decreasing proportions of oil and polysaccharide in the sample. Decreases in pH values with increasing proportions of the oil fraction in emulsion gels were also reported for samples stabilized by κ -carrageenan, chemically similar to furcellaran [38]. The optimum pH value of investigated model systems depends on their intended application and the specific bioactive substance they are designed to carrier. Emulgels used as cosmetics or skin-applied medicines must have a pH within 6.5, which prevents irritation of the skin [39]. In food, on the other hand, the pH of the product is very important from the perspective of microbiological stability. Refrigerated storage of the furcellaran – safflower oil emulsion gels resulted in a slight decrease in the pH values of all tested variants, while the differences in values between day 7 and day 14 were not statistically significant. No correlation was observed between the decrease in pH and the content of the polysaccharide and oil fraction in the systems. However, in none of the formulation variants was the pH value difference measured between day 1 and day 7 > 8 %. Despite the lack of differences in consistency and appearance of the emulgels after one week of storage, the decrease in pH value can be explained by a minor partial autohydrolysis or esterification of the polysaccharide due to the effect of free fatty acids [40]. Since, in addition to pH, storage stability is also determined by other factors such as water activity, the presence of substances that inhibit the growth of microorganisms and type of packaging, future research will focus on reducing the water activity of emulgels (e.g., through the addition of sorbitol) and the addition of natural extracts with antibacterial activity.

3.1.3. Zeta potential

Fig. 2 shows the zeta potential values of the tested emulsion gels. Zeta potential of furcellaran is approx. -40 mV [41], and of safflower oil is -29.29 ± 1.99 mV. The obtained results suggest that furcellaran dominated the overall structure of the gels as well as the electrical characteristics of the material. The highest values were recorded for the lowest oil concentrations, regardless of the furcellaran concentration used. However, the highest stability was observed in the case of emulsion gels with a concentration of 2.0 % furcellaran. The greatest decrease in stability with increasing oil addition was observed in emulgels with 3.0 % furcellaran concentration. Both FUR and safflower oil were negative, which may suggest that electrostatic repulsion occurs between

Fig. 1. Swelling ratio values of emulgels with different furcellaran and safflower oil concentration.

Table 2

The pH changes of emulgels at 1, 7 and 14 day of cold-storage.

Furcellaran concentration [%]	Oil concentration [%]	DAY 1 ^B	DAY 7 ^A	DAY 14 ^A
2.0	5.0	6.79 ± 0.09 ^j	6.54 ± 0.27 ^j	6.50 ± 0.06 ^l
	10.0	6.30 ± 0.08 ^{gh}	6.28 ± 0.23 ^{ij}	6.29 ± 0.08 ^{kl}
	15.0	6.06 ± 0.04 ^{efg}	5.91 ± 0.05 ^{ghi}	5.78 ± 0.27 ^{ghij}
	20.0	5.42 ± 0.04 ^c	5.34 ± 0.11 ^{def}	5.18 ± 0.29 ^{cdef}
2.5	5.0	6.72 ± 0.13 ^{ij}	6.34 ± 0.07 ^{ij}	6.39 ± 0.50 ^{kl}
	10.0	6.24 ± 0.06 ^{fg}	5.95 ± 0.18 ^{hi}	5.95 ± 0.31 ^{ghijk}
	15.0	5.94 ± 0.04 ^{de}	5.74 ± 0.09 ^{efgh}	5.67 ± 0.26 ^{fghi}
	20.0	5.38 ± 0.01 ^c	5.25 ± 0.06 ^d	5.13 ± 0.27 ^{cde}
3.0	5.0	6.51 ± 0.03 ^{hi}	6.02 ± 0.04 ^{hi}	6.09 ± 0.52 ^{ijkl}
	10.0	6.04 ± 0.05 ^{ef}	5.78 ± 0.12 ^{fgh}	5.69 ± 0.40 ^{fghi}
	15.0	5.73 ± 0.07 ^d	5.50 ± 0.21 ^{defg}	5.52 ± 0.22 ^{efgh}
	20.0	5.26 ± 0.08 ^c	5.17 ± 0.02 ^{cd}	5.05 ± 0.29 ^{cde}
3.5	5.0	6.01 ± 0.11 ^{ef}	5.91 ± 0.02 ^{ghi}	5.75 ± 0.26 ^{fghi}
	10.0	5.82 ± 0.03 ^{de}	5.41 ± 0.28 ^{def}	5.41 ± 0.57 ^{defg}
	15.0	5.17 ± 0.07 ^c	5.06 ± 0.06 ^{cd}	4.96 ± 0.25 ^{bcd}
	20.0	4.85 ± 0.12 ^b	4.74 ± 0.21 ^{bc}	4.68 ± 0.11 ^{abc}
4.0	5.0	5.42 ± 0.05 ^c	5.32 ± 0.09 ^{de}	5.18 ± 0.26 ^{cdef}
	10.0	4.63 ± 0.06 ^{ab}	4.46 ± 0.09 ^{ab}	4.46 ± 0.09 ^{ab}
	15.0	4.60 ± 0.21 ^{ab}	4.34 ± 0.05 ^{ab}	4.29 ± 0.27 ^a
	20.0	4.49 ± 0.05 ^a	4.29 ± 0.14 ^a	4.21 ± 0.35 ^a

Average values ± standard deviation from replicates. Different letters in the same column with different letters and significantly different ($p < 0.05$); different capital letter as superscript statistically significant.

Fig. 2. Effect of emulgels composition on zeta potential values.

these molecules. Therefore, numerous hydrogen bonds could have formed in the gel structure between the FUR and safflower oil functional groups [42]. The zeta potential parameter values of most formulations (excluding those with 3.0 % FUR) were within the range to maintain the stability of the materials during their storage. Greater stability of the preparation is expected to ensure longer storage [43].

3.2. Textural characteristics of emulgels

The texture of a food is determined by the orientation and interaction of its various components affecting their stability and release in the digestive tract as well as determining consumer acceptance. The results of the TPA analysis for the emulgels systems including the effect of safflower oil content and furcellaran concentration are shown in Table 3.

Hardness, determined as the resistive peak force, indicates directly emulgel strength. The values of this parameter calculated for furcellaran - safflower oil systems ranged between 1.06 and 13.53 N. The strength of

emulgels depended, as expected, on both the concentration of the gelling agent and the amount of added oil. It was found that, doubling the amount of furcellaran results in an almost sevenfold increase in the hardness of samples containing 5 % oil addition. In contrast, increasing the proportion of the fat fraction in the system resulted in a weakening of the sample structure. The decrease in hardness of gelled emulsions with increasing fat content is also presented for surimi gel - coconut oil [44] and sunflower and soy oil emulsion gels systems [11]. The type of relationship between the strength of the emulgels and the amount of fat fraction in the sample indicates the nature of the interactions between the matrix and the filling. Hardness increasing with the proportion of fat in the sample indicates the chemical nature of the binding of oil droplets in the matrix. In contrast, the decrease in hardness with increasing oil addition, as observed in our study, suggests that the fat droplets are only physically immobilized in the polymer matrix [45]. Thus, it can be concluded that safflower oil has a low affinity for furcellaran in the studied systems, and as a result, weakens the polymer network. Based on

Table 3
Textural parameters values of furcellaran - safflower oil emulgel systems.

Furcellaran concentration [%]	Oil concentration [%]	HARDNESS [N]	SPRINGINESS	COHESIVENESS	GUMMINESS [N]
2.0	5.0	2.05 ± 0.33 ^{cd}	0.744 ± 0.09 ^{cdef}	0.119 ± 0.02 ^{bcd}	0.27 ± 0.05 ^{de}
	10.0	1.48 ± 0.24 ^{bcd}	0.857 ± 0.11 ^{defg}	0.123 ± 0.01 ^{bcd}	0.17 ± 0.02 ^{abc}
	15.0	1.37 ± 0.10 ^{abc}	1.042 ± 0.21 ^{gh}	0.136 ± 0.02 ^{cde}	0.14 ± 0.02 ^{ab}
2.5	5.0	1.06 ± 0.34 ^a	1.32 ± 0.19 ^h	0.221 ± 0.05 ^e	0.13 ± 0.00 ^a
	10.0	3.17 ± 0.58 ^{ef}	0.711 ± 0.05 ^{abcdef}	0.107 ± 0.03 ^{abcd}	0.38 ± 0.08 ^f
	15.0	3.52 ± 0.77 ^{fgh}	0.729 ± 0.06 ^{abcdefg}	0.110 ± 0.03 ^{abcde}	0.23 ± 0.03 ^{cde}
3.0	5.0	2.1 ± 0.52 ^{cd}	0.813 ± 0.10 ^{defg}	0.113 ± 0.01 ^{abcd}	0.22 ± 0.02 ^d
	10.0	1.11 ± 0.13 ^{ab}	1.255 ± 0.05 ^h	0.151 ± 0.02 ^{de}	0.17 ± 0.02 ^{bc}
	15.0	7.30 ± 0.94 ^{jk}	0.576 ± 0.10 ^{ab}	0.092 ± 0.03 ^{abc}	0.74 ± 0.08 ^{hi}
3.5	5.0	5.93 ± 0.49 ^{hij}	0.728 ± 0.09 ^{defg}	0.098 ± 0.03 ^{abcd}	0.7 ± 0.05 ^h
	10.0	4.71 ± 0.65 ^{ghi}	0.785 ± 0.05 ^{bcd}	0.102 ± 0.03 ^{abcd}	0.47 ± 0.09 ^g
	15.0	2.38 ± 0.20 ^{de}	0.938 ± 0.08 ^{efgh}	0.124 ± 0.03 ^{bcd}	0.37 ± 0.06 ^{ef}
4.0	5.0	10.35 ± 0.86 ^l	0.573 ± 0.12 ^{abc}	0.072 ± 0.00 ^{ab}	0.97 ± 0.06 ⁱ
	10.0	6.54 ± 0.80 ^{ijk}	0.673 ± 0.12 ^{abcd}	0.088 ± 0.03 ^{abcd}	0.72 ± 0.05 ^h
	15.0	5.18 ± 0.59 ^{ghi}	0.767 ± 0.07 ^{defg}	0.092 ± 0.02 ^{abcd}	0.54 ± 0.03 ^g
4.0	5.0	3.78 ± 0.59 ^{fg}	0.931 ± 0.08 ^{efgh}	0.099 ± 0.03 ^{abcd}	0.4 ± 0.02 ^f
	10.0	13.53 ± 0.85 ^m	0.550 ± 0.04 ^a	0.064 ± 0.03 ^a	1.36 ± 0.02 ^j
	15.0	9.63 ± 1.20 ^{lm}	0.669 ± 0.10 ^{abcd}	0.083 ± 0.04 ^{ab}	0.88 ± 0.01 ^{hi}
	20.0	7.93 ± 1.30 ^{kl}	0.687 ± 0.08 ^{bcdf}	0.092 ± 0.04 ^{abcd}	0.76 ± 0.07 ^{hi}
	20.0	4.61 ± 0.56 ^{gh}	0.824 ± 0.03 ^{defg}	0.097 ± 0.02 ^{abcd}	0.49 ± 0.02 ^g

ANOVA (F-ratio)	Hardness	Springiness	Cohesiveness	Gumminess
Furcellaran concentration	30.09*	10.07*	1.05	15.6*
Oil concentration	4.47*	4.56*	3.75*	4.31*
Interaction	2.18*	2.83*	1.00	3.36*

Average values ± standard deviation from replicates. Different letters in the same column with different letters and significantly different ($p < 0.05$); * statistically significant with $p < 0.05$.

the F-ratio obtained by two-factor analysis of variance, it was found that the hardness of furcellaran - safflower oil emulgels was determined more by the concentration of the gelling agent than by the amount of incorporated oil. The springiness expresses the rate of deformation recovery when deformed sample goes back to its original form after deforming tension removal. Values of springiness determined for tested emulsion gels were related to both furcellaran and oil concentrations while the content of the polymer showed a greater effect. All studied samples showed an increase in springiness with increasing amounts of safflower oil which may be due to the plasticizing effect of fat [46]. It was also noted that an increase in furcellaran concentration in turn resulted in a decrease in springiness. In contrast to gelatine, furcellaran forms very brittle gels [47], which may explain the lower elasticity of systems with a higher proportion of this biopolymer. Based on the cohesiveness value, the tendency of the material to stick together can be determined. Increasing oil addition with decreasing furcellaran concentration caused a successive increase in the cohesiveness of the investigated emulgels although only the effect of the fat fraction in the sample can be considered statistically significant. An increase in cohesion due to the increasing proportion of fat in the material structure was observed for alginate-based [10] and protein stabilized [20,21] emulgels. Interestingly, only the oil content in the sample had a significant impact on the calculated cohesiveness values. Gumminess is a very important quality descriptor of the semi-solid materials such as gels or emulsions [48]. Since it was known that high hardness cause high gumminess [49] the values of this parameter for furcellaran - safflower oil systems showed the same trend as hardness – values raised with increasing polymer concentration and decreasing oil addition. The content of individual fractions in the material as well as the interactions between them had a significant impact on the determined gumminess values.

3.3. Mechanical properties of emulgels

Mechanical properties next to textural parameters have a great influence on the sensation during consumption of semi-solid food products

by which has effect on the consumer acceptance. For example, the value of elastic modulus can be connected with the perception of the product hardness and fracture stress is often correlate with attributes perceived at first bite of food. However, since food products are very often complex multi-component systems, the correlations between their individual components mean that mechanical parameters are determined experimentally [50]. In our research compression test was carried out to determine mechanical behaviour of furcellaran – safflower oil emulgels and to investigate the effect of increasing furcellaran concentration and oil content. Values of elastic modulus, fracture energy (work) and fracture stress plotted from the stress – strain curves were shown in Table 4.

Fracture stress values of tested emulgels varied between 20.84 and 186.23 kPa and showed a clear upward trend with increasing furcellaran concentration. Since fracture stress is a parameter that expresses, in a way, the strength of the material, the observed tendency was as expected. Similar correlations have been observed for other polysaccharide gels such as alginate [51] and pectin [52]. For each concentration of furcellaran, a successive decrease of fracture stress value was also observed with increasing proportion of oil in the sample. It has been shown that fracture is affected not only by the amount of individual components in the emulsion, but also by heterogeneous features of the network structure, resulting from the nature of the gelling agent or the gelation temperature [34]. Sala et al. [53] showed that increasing oil addition affected the increase in fracture stress values in whey protein gels, while the opposite trend was observed for carrageenan-stabilized samples. In furcellaran - safflower oil systems, the addition of a fat fraction evidently weakens the structure of the emulgels, which agreed with mentioned study due to structural similarities in carrageenan and furcellaran. A decrease of fracture stress values with increasing oil addition was also observed for agar-stabilized emulsion gels [54]. Statistically significant effects on the fracture stress values of the tested emulgels were observed for the concentration of the gelling agent, the amount of oil added as well as interactions between the two, however, the concentration of furcellaran was the most

Table 4

Mechanical properties of furcellaran - safflower oil emulgels obtained by uniaxial compression tests.

Furcellaran concentration [%]	Oil concentration [%]	Fracture Stress [kPa]	Fracture Energy [mJ]	Elastic modulus [kPa]
2.5	5.0	69.15 ± 1.28 ^{cde}	7.46 ± 0.09 ^{bc}	275.7 ± 5.58 ^{efg}
	10.0	58.99 ± 6.01 ^c	6.17 ± 0.73 ^{bc}	246.8 ± 7.06 ^{cde}
	15.0	37.81 ± 2.08 ^{ab}	4.89 ± 0.61 ^b	168.32 ± 3.75 ^{ab}
3.0	20.0	20.84 ± 0.62 ^a	1.76 ± 0.04 ^a	140.46 ± 4.42 ^a
	5.0	85.47 ± 3.07 ^{efg}	14.25 ± 1.5 ^d	311.78 ± 21.77 ^{fgh}
	10.0	78.55 ± 4.16 ^{def}	9.02 ± 0.77 ^c	261.41 ± 7.66 ^{def}
	15.0	66.86 ± 3.15 ^{cd}	6.99 ± 0.16 ^{bc}	239.39 ± 9.02 ^{cde}
3.5	20.0	39.13 ± 3.72 ^b	6.38 ± 0.36 ^{bc}	201.1 ± 3.36 ^{bc}
	5.0	121.01 ± 11.05 ^h	18.21 ± 1.94 ^e	405.12 ± 12.77 ⁱ
	10.0	94.48 ± 3.5 ^{fg}	14.58 ± 0.55 ^d	344.15 ± 22.87 ^h
	15.0	66.59 ± 3.83 ^{cd}	8.33 ± 0.55 ^c	264.28 ± 46.03 ^{def}
4.0	20.0	40.03 ± 3.75 ^b	5.03 ± 0.49 ^b	211.18 ± 0.76 ^{bcd}
	5.0	186.23 ± 8.8 ^j	34.86 ± 1.15 ^f	519.43 ± 24 ^j
	10.0	151.9 ± 7.64 ⁱ	27.79 ± 1.74 ^f	477.03 ± 22.03 ^j
	15.0	96.78 ± 9.65 ^g	16.02 ± 1.75 ^{de}	322.76 ± 30.96 ^{gh}
	20.0	64.95 ± 4.24 ^{cd}	7.88 ± 0.48 ^{bc}	312.7 ± 15.24 ^{fgh}

ANOVA (F-ratio)	Fracture stress	Fracture work	Elastic modulus
Furcellaran concentration	11.48*	22.90*	10.07*
Oil concentration	5.31*	6.02*	2.38
Interaction	2.80*	3.24*	2.56*

Average values ± standard deviation from replicates. Different letters in the same column with different letters and significantly different ($p < 0.05$); * statistically significant with $p < 0.05$.

significant.

Elastic modulus (E) determined as the ratio of stress to strain material during the linear limit of elasticity expresses the rigidity of the material. Food rigidity increases with increasing value of E [55]. The determined values of elastic modulus were determined mainly by furcellaran content in material, rather less from the interaction between the contents of the polysaccharide and fat fractions, while the impact of oil addition on E values was statistically insignificant. As expected, an increase in the concentration of gelling agent in the sample resulted in a significant increase in the rigidity of the material while increasing oil addition decreased the E values of emulgels. The effect of oil addition on elastic modulus relates not to the amount of fat fraction in material, but to the interactions between the oil droplets and the hydrocolloid matrix. According to Van der Poel theory, an increase in E-value as a result of oil addition is observed in emulsion gels with bound droplets while the effect is exactly the opposite for materials with unbound droplets [53]. The tested emulgel systems may contain unbound oil droplets in the form of aggregates whose increasing volume reduces the elastic modulus of the polymer matrix [34]. Similar observation was reported for kappa-carrageenan emulsion gels produced with rapeseed oil [54].

Fracture energy determined from the area under the curve up to fracture. Similarly, elastic modulus is related to the hardness and fracturability of the material [50]. There was a statistically significant effect on the obtained G values of the furcellaran - safflower oil systems, with both independent variables and the interaction between them, while furcellaran concentration was most notable. As with parameter E, fracture energy increased with increasing furcellaran content and decreasing oil additions. Decreasing fracture energy as a result of increased corn oil addition was also observed for carrageenan and agar-based emulgels [56]. The obtained mechanical test results coincided with the TPA analysis data, indicating that the increasing proportion of oil in the material weakens its overall strength. Nevertheless, in food or cosmetic applications, high product hardness is not always desirable. The wide range of obtained results means that the final properties of the furcellaran - safflower oil system can be designed by changing the proportion of individual components. In addition, future research will also include modifying the pH or enriching the formulation with other ingredients, which will potentially affect the mechanical and textural properties of emulgels.

3.4. Colour analysis of emulgels

The colour properties of emulgels are also very important and may have a determining impact on consumer acceptance. The emulgel colour parameters including lightness (L^*), redness (a^*), yellowness (b^*), whiteness index (WI) and yellowness index (YI) were shown in Table 5 and Fig. 3. Regardless of the FUR concentration used, all values of colour parameters increased with the increase of safflower oil.

The L^* parameter (brightness) values were quite high, with a tendency towards white. Additionally, WI was found to increase with increasing oil concentration, regardless of the FUR concentration used. Changes in WI of the gel sample may reflect changes in the structure of the gel network, which may result from potential interactions between the polysaccharide and the oil. The emulsified oil was evenly distributed in the polysaccharide matrix, which led to a stronger light scattering effect and higher light reflectance values in the gels. Similar conclusions were reached by Song et al. [34] obtained *Nemipterus Virgatus* Surimi Gel enriched with Safflower Seed Oil. Parameter b^* describes the degree of yellowness/blueness of the material and takes positive values for yellowish colour and negative values for bluish colour. As the oil concentration increased, an increase in the value of the b^* parameter was noted, which indicates the yellowing of the gels. Moreover, with the increase in the concentration of the added oil, an increase in the intensity of the reddish colour (parameter a^*) was noted, which can be attributed to the colour of the oil. YI values increased with increasing oil addition at each FUR concentration, however, the highest increase was observed in the case of FUR concentrations of 2.0 and 2.5 %. Safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius*) has yellow and red pigments from the flavonoid subclass, quinochalcone C-glycosides, which are found only in this species [57]. In seed oil safflower, the dominant carotenoids were β -cryptoxanthin and β -carotene, which are responsible for the yellow-red colour [58].

3.5. Thermal characteristics of emulgels

The thermal properties of emulsion gels containing different concentrations of furcellaran and safflower oil were determined based on an endotherm ranging from - 80 to 200 °C, an example of which is shown in Fig. 4. The most visible transitions observed in the investigated range

Table 5
Colour parameters values of furcellaran – safflower oil emulsion gels.

Parameter	5 % oil	10 % oil	15 % oil	20 % oil
2.0 % furcellaran				
L*	74.13 ± 2.68 ^{ab}	74.62 ± 2.78 ^{ab}	76.02 ± 1.44 ^{abc}	78.83 ± 2.81 ^{abcde}
a*	-0.44 ± 0.04 ^a	-0.25 ± 0.08 ^{abcd}	-0.07 ± 0.07 ^{def}	0.14 ± 0.11 ^{fgh}
b*	5.79 ± 0.37 ^{ab}	7.84 ± 0.6 ^{cde}	9.05 ± 0.28 ^{efg}	10.67 ± 1.49 ^{ghi}
2.5 % furcellaran				
L*	72.75 ± 2.18 ^a	74.89 ± 2.07 ^{ab}	75.55 ± 1.45 ^{abc}	79.26 ± 2.66 ^{bcde}
a*	-0.32 ± 0.07 ^{abc}	-0.05 ± 0.03 ^{def}	-0.2 ± 0.08 ^{bcd}	0.22 ± 0.02 ^{gh}
b*	6.36 ± 0.24 ^{abc}	7.92 ± 0.3 ^{cde}	9.4 ± 0.91 ^{efgh}	12.87 ± 1.01 ⁱ
3.0 % furcellaran				
L*	75.24 ± 2.84 ^{abc}	76.95 ± 2.87 ^{abcd}	78.38 ± 3.86 ^{abcde}	84.6 ± 2.97 ^e
a*	-0.37 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	-0.14 ± 0.06 ^{cde}	-0.06 ± 0.04 ^{def}	0.26 ± 0.07 ^h
b*	6.14 ± 0.61 ^{ab}	8.27 ± 0.51 ^{def}	9.54 ± 0.88 ^{efgh}	11.17 ± 0.77 ^{hi}
3.5 % furcellaran				
L*	73.73 ± 3.13 ^{ab}	79.23 ± 1 ^{bcde}	80.13 ± 3.47 ^{bcde}	82.8 ± 3.87 ^{de}
a*	-0.25 ± 0.09 ^{abcd}	0.02 ± 0.09 ^{efg}	0.09 ± 0.08 ^{fgh}	0.21 ± 0.03 ^{gh}
b*	5.57 ± 0.72 ^a	7.23 ± 1 ^{bcd}	8.59 ± 1.05 ^{def}	10.22 ± 1.04 ^{fgh}
4.0 % furcellaran				
L*	77.87 ± 1.0 ^{abcd}	80.56 ± 3.72 ^{abcde}	81.19 ± 2.66 ^{cde}	82.66 ± 3.58 ^{de}
a*	-0.13 ± 0.14 ^{cde}	0.02 ± 0.17 ^{efg}	0.23 ± 0.12 ^h	0.23 ± 0.12 ^h
b*	6.61 ± 0.59 ^{abc}	7.8 ± 0.79 ^{cde}	8.96 ± 0.61 ^{efg}	9.88 ± 0.77 ^{fgh}

Average values ± standard deviation from replicates. Different letters in the same row with various letters and significantly different ($p < 0.05$); 2.0 %F, 2.5 %F, 3.0 %F means 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 % of furcellaran while A = 5 %, B = 10 %, C = 15 and D = 20 % of safflower oil addition.

were melting water/fat crystals occurring around 0 °C and thermal degradation of the whole structure appearing above 100 °C. In contrast, melting, which has great importance for analysing the stability of gels and gelled emulsions, was a much less energetic transition, essentially invisible when the entire range of the thermogram was observed. Furcellaran – safflower oil emulgels melting was characterised based on three temperatures describing the transition: initial (To), middle (Tm) and end (Te), with the second one considered as the melting point. The obtained temperature values with the corresponding enthalpy of the transition are shown in Table 6. All temperature values showed the same trend: they increased with increasing fraction of furcellaran and decreasing oil content in the sample. Melting point values ranged from 31.3 °C (2.0 % FUR and 20 % oil) to 80.2 °C (4.0 % FUR and 5 % oil). The Tm value of gels and emulgels is a combination of very many factors. The thermal destabilisation of the furcellaran matrix can be influenced by the presence of ions, the number and position of sulphate groups and, above all, the nature of the interactions with other components of the system. Tuvikene et al. [59] reported that the melting temperature of 1.5 % furcellaran gels can range from 35.5 to 63.8 °C depending on their origin. Tested emulgels became more thermally stable as a result of increasing the concentration of the gelling agent. Based on the correlation between this observation and the high values of mechanical and textural parameters, it can be assumed that the increase in Tm is associated with a strengthening of the matrix structure. Improvement of thermal stability due to increasing addition of gelling agent was also reported for gels with κ-carrageenan [60]. The decrease in melting point with increasing oil addition can be explained by the disruption of the order and integrity of the polysaccharide matrix due to the presence of more fat droplets in the system.

Enthalpy of a transition expressing the amount of energy required for the phenomenon to occur. The values determined for furcellaran - safflower oil systems, like the melting point, increased with increasing polysaccharide content while increasing oil addition affected their decreases. Thus, the stable and ordered structures formed in samples containing high furcellaran concentrations required more energy for their disintegration.

3.6. Microstructure of emulsion gels

The morphological properties of furcellaran-safflower oil emulgels were observed through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Sample images depicting 2.0 %, 3.0 %, and 4.0 % furcellaran emulsion gels with additions of 5 % and 20 % safflower oil are shown in Fig. 5. In all studied systems, an amorphous polysaccharide matrix was observed as a typical fibrous structure. In samples with lower polysaccharide concentrations, an accumulation of a “sponge-like” phase can be observed in the main matrix of the gel network with boundaries visible as darkening of the material. The surface of emulgels with a 4.0 % concentration of furcellaran appeared to be more homogeneous and less dimensional with areas transforming to a practically smooth amorphous surface. Pores with a shape on the cross-section similar to an oval, clearly reaching deep into the material with diameters varying from tens to hundreds of micrometres are more visible at lower concentrations of polysaccharide. In some areas, large-diameter oil droplets are visible on the matrix structure, which may support the hypothesis that they do not interact with the matrix and inhibit the formation of a tight polymeric matrix. This would then explain the decrease in hardness or strength of the gels as the proportion of oil in the sample increases. The same lack of interaction between agar matrix and oil was observed by Kim et al. [61].

3.7. X-ray diffraction analysis of emulgels

Fig. 6 (a-b) shows XRD patterns of the sample series with increasing furcellaran concentration and maximum and minimum safflower oil additions. Regardless of gelling agent concentration and safflower oil content, all emulgels were strongly amorphous, as broad peaks indicated. Emulgels containing 5 % oil showed three broad peaks at 2θ regions of 10–12°, 25–27°, and 40–45°. It can be assumed that the first peak was involved in the ordered structure of the molecule resulting from the distance between FUR chains [62]. The second and third peaks were associated with the multiscale structure of the molecule. A higher furcellaran concentration was found to raise the intensity of the predominant peak. A similar increase in spectral intensity due to a higher ratio of gelling agent was observed in systems stabilized with

Fig. 3. Whiteness index (a) and yellowness index (b) of emulgels with different furcellaran and safflower oil concentration.

κ -carrageenan [63]. Therefore, considering a similar chemical structure of two algal polysaccharides, it can be assumed that the above peaks indicate mutual interactions, for example, involving the sulphate groups, which exist in every fourth FUR monomer unit. Furthermore, a higher hydrophobic fraction enhances the peak intensity at the 2 θ region of 10–12°, especially for emulgels holding 2.0 and 2.5 % of furcellaran.

Fig. 6 (c-d) shows the XRD data as a function of scattering vector Q . It is assumed that correlations above $Q = 1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ are intrachains in amorphous materials, while macromolecules exhibit interchain interactions. The weaker peak at 2.17 \AA found in all emulsion formulations may be due to cation-functional group interactions, contributing to the FUR polymer chain rigidity. These may be intramolecular bridges formed by an ionic bond between K^+ and the sulphate group of the one D-galactose residue or by an electrostatic bond between K^+ and the anhydro-O-3,6-ring of the other D-galactose residue [64]. The peak at 3.14 \AA may result from interactions between functional sulfate groups of the polymer matrix disturbed by oil microparticles. In turn, correlations of 4.39 \AA result from the excessive fat fraction in the hydrogel matrix, where liquid oil is not bound in the emulgel structure but only physically immobilized [65]. Higher peak intensities above 7 \AA and at 4.39 \AA

detected for samples with 20 % oil fraction indicate that the safflower oil acted as an “interaction booster.” Thus, one can assume that emulgels with maximum safflower oil can be a plasticizer for furcellaran chains. These observations are confirmed by emulgels with weaker mechanical parameters and a higher melting point due to the 20 % safflower oil.

4. Conclusions

Final properties of furcellaran - safflower oil systems were dependent on polysaccharide and fat fraction concentrations. It was found that oil acted as an inactive-filler in the studied materials which means that it was not bounded chemically but only physically immobilized in polymer matrix. It was observed that increasing the proportion of furcellaran with decreasing addition of safflower oil results in more structured, hard and strong emulgels. For example, the fracture stress value of system with 5 % oil additions increased from 69.15 for 186.23 kPa and hardness from 2.05 to 13.53 N as a result of doubling the concentration of the gelling agent. A similar trend was observed for the elastic modulus, gumminess or melting point values determined by using DSC. Similarly, the pH values, immediately after production as well as after storage for

Fig. 4. Typical thermogram of furcellaran/safflower oil emulgels containing 2 % of furcellaran and 5 % (2.0F-A) and 20 % of safflower oil (2.0 %F-D).

Table 6

Thermal characteristic values of furcellaran – safflower oil emulsion gels obtained by DSC.

Furcellaran concentration [%]	Oil concentration [%]	To [°C]	Tm [°C]	Te [°C]	ΔH [J/g]
2.0	5.0	46.6 ± 1.2 ^{cde}	48.0 ± 1.4 ^{cde}	49.0 ± 1.5 ^{bcd}	0.125 ± 0.034 ^{ab}
	10.0	44.2 ± 1.7 ^{cd}	46.1 ± 1.2 ^{cd}	47.4 ± 1.0 ^{bcd}	0.098 ± 0.017 ^{ab}
	15.0	35.8 ± 2.6 ^{ab}	37.4 ± 1.2 ^{ab}	39.3 ± 1.8 ^{ab}	0.085 ± 0.029 ^{ab}
	20.0	29.3 ± 1.4 ^a	31.3 ± 1.3 ^a	32.7 ± 1.5 ^a	0.058 ± 0.012 ^a
2.5	5.0	53.4 ± 0.2 ^{efghi}	55.1 ± 0.5 ^{efgh}	57.3 ± 1.8 ^{defgh}	0.163 ± 0.117 ^{ab}
	10.0	49.8 ± 2.2 ^{cdefg}	51.4 ± 1.6 ^{cdef}	53.6 ± 1.8 ^{cdefg}	0.144 ± 0.003 ^{ab}
	15.0	43.9 ± 2.1 ^{cd}	46.6 ± 3.1 ^{cd}	50.8 ± 5.5 ^{cde}	0.128 ± 0.061 ^{ab}
	20.0	43.3 ± 3.4 ^{bc}	44.6 ± 3.6 ^{bc}	45.7 ± 3.6 ^{bc}	0.057 ± 0.045 ^a
3.0	5.0	55 ± 0.5 ^{0fghi}	55.9 ± 2.3 ^{fghi}	59.0 ± 1.5 ^{efgh}	0.193 ± 0.056 ^b
	10.0	51.3 ± 2.0 ^{defgh}	52.4 ± 2.0 ^{defg}	58.5 ± 1.3 ^{efgh}	0.144 ± 0.061 ^{ab}
	15.0	45 ± 3.4 ^{0cd}	49.6 ± 0.9 ^{0cdef}	51.1 ± 6.0 ^{0cde}	0.135 ± 0.045 ^{ab}
	20.0	43.6 ± 2.8 ^{cd}	45.7 ± 3.2 ^{cd}	46.7 ± 3.2 ^{bc}	0.093 ± 0.027 ^{ab}
3.5	5.0	57.3 ± 4.6 ^{ghij}	62.1 ± 1.7 ^{hi}	63.7 ± 1.6 ^{gh}	0.196 ± 0.006 ^a
	10.0	58.8 ± 5.2 ^{hij}	61.5 ± 2.9 ^{hi}	63.2 ± 2.6 ^{gh}	0.138 ± 0.008 ^{ab}
	15.0	53.3 ± 2.0 ^{efghi}	55.4 ± 1.7 ^{efgh}	56.9 ± 2.4 ^{defgh}	0.106 ± 0.002 ^{ab}
	20.0	48.5 ± 1.2 ^{cdef}	50.8 ± 0.4 ^{cdef}	52.2 ± 0.7 ^{cdef}	0.085 ± 0.009 ^{ab}
4.0	5.0	74.7 ± 2.6 ^k	80.2 ± 3.3 ^j	85.4 ± 6.3 ⁱ	0.345 ± 0.025 ^c
	10.0	62.0 ± 1.4 ^j	63.3 ± 1.1 ⁱ	64.4 ± 1.2 ^h	0.154 ± 0.026 ^{ab}
	15.0	60.7 ± 1.4 ^{ij}	62.4 ± 1.4 ^{hi}	63.7 ± 1.8 ^{gh}	0.109 ± 0.004 ^{ab}
	20.0	53.8 ± 1.8 ^{efghi}	60.1 ± 6.7 ^{ghi}	61.3 ± 6.7 ^{fgh}	0.086 ± 0.061 ^{ab}

Average values ± standard deviation from replicates. Different letters in the same column with different letters and significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

several days, were higher in samples with a lower oil content and higher furcellaran concentration. On the other hand, the swelling ratio of the investigated emulgels increased with increasing the proportion of both polysaccharide and oil fraction. The increasing proportion of oil also had a positive effect on the fullness of the sample colour. Due to the differing effects of the oil and polysaccharide on specific functional properties, it is difficult to identify a single optimal formulation without knowing its exact application. Studied emulgels may be applied as food or cosmetic carriers of active compounds. Regardless of the formulation, all

emulsion variants were found to have a firm and stable structure, which suggests that they will have a protective effect on lipophilic bioactive compounds, limiting their oxidation or delaying absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Therefore, based on the reported characteristics of systems containing 2.0 to 4.0 % furcellaran and 5 to 20 % safflower oil, the next stages of the project will focus on investigating the compatibility of specific active compounds with oil and polysaccharide matrixes. It is also intended to verify how the reduction of water activity and the modification of pH will affect the characteristics of the emulgels. The

Fig. 5. SEM image (magnification of 100 \times) of emulsions containing 2.0, 3.0 and 4.0 % of furcellaran and 5 and 20 % safflower oil; sample code with A: 5 % oil addition, sample code with D: 20 % oil addition,

Fig. 6. XRD patterns of emulsions stabilized by different furcellaran concentration (2.0–4.0 %) with different oil addition (A-D: 5 to 20 %) showed in scale of angle (a-b) and Q-value (c-d).

potential application of furcellaran-safflower oil materials in the food industry will also require storage and microbiological analyses.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anna Stępień: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lesław**

Juszczak: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Beata Synkiewicz-Musialska:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Piotr Zachariasz:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Ewelina Jamróz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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